

ADVANCED METHODOLOGY OF INTRODUCING NOVEL WORK PATTERNS FOR CORPORATES IN INDIA

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Abstract: Innovation in business practices encompasses innovative creations and new methods of doing business. In the present business environment, the success of the business depends hugely upon the quick adoption of modern techniques of production, processes and maintenance of workers. The growth and productivity of the business can now only be increased through strengthening of internal factors as the external factors are beyond the control. Empirical evidences have been obtained which suggests that by overhauling the way how the business processes are executed, an organization can witness rise in the output efficiency level by up to 12%. Thereby providing an alternative mechanism for boosting an organization's profitability margins under today's dynamic and extremely competitive business industry. This research paper embarks upon researching the extent of productivity enhancement that can be brought in a business organization through implementing innovative work practices thereby reshaping an organizations internal business outlook. The research methodology applied utilizes the participatory observation coalesced with active research. The research has been conducted around what kind of work behavior innovations can be introduced in an enterprise which can result in twin sided benefits of reducing the attrition rate by increasing the employee satisfaction index and increasing the profitability of the implementing organization. The research results yielded fascinating conclusions about how work space and work behavior can be reinvented with much simplicity and at affordable costs. Innovative practices researched include free address workspace, agile working methodology, activity based working, application of work at home policies, reduced working hours policy, shared infrastructure and collaborative working etc.

Keywords: Workspace transformation, Innovative work behavior, Innovative workspace, Productivity advancement

1. Introduction

Gone are the days when employees were hired with the sole objective of getting work done. With two decades of the 21st century passing by, the employer – employee relationship has transformed much beyond than a master – servant liaison. Today the expenditure on employee benefits mark a colossal mark in the profit and loss account of major MNC's. The amount of employee benefits expenditures made by tech giants Google, Facebook, Amazon and Netflix amounts to be equivalent to the GDP of Commonwealth of Dominica, an island country in the West Indies. The organizations have undoubtedly agreed the need for providing their employees better working conditions. The question therefore arises that where on the one side the business entities are already facing immense competition resulting in reduced revenues and on the other side the expenditures are surging up speedily, so how to maintain the profitability of the business. High net worth companies can although sustain surviving with low profits in the long run, however the small and medium sector can witness an entire wipe out if an immediate solution is not worked upon.

There have been ongoing discussions in this regard. The solutions that came up were either to boost the sales by diminishing the cost of materials or increase the productivity of the employees. While the former measure can result in deteriorated quality of the product which can be detrimental in the long term interests of the business the latter measure seems to be the only workable elucidation. Rise in the productivity of employees implies bringing better quality output in reduced time period. This requires recruitment of better talent. The most deliberated topic in this regard has been then how to attract better

talent and how to retain that talent. How about creating a team with only the smartest human resources available in the industry?

While every organization strives towards gathering best of the best personnel empirical evidences suggests that even a team filled with all the greatest employees will not exceed in providing better output results than a team comprising employees with multiple aptitude but full of gratitude towards the organization. For instance in a team of only best performers, the imperative requirement of having the “We” quotient in a team is replaced with the “I” or “Me” quotient which proves to be detrimental in the long term interests of the business.

Therefore the organizations are left with improvising the existing working conditions and making them more habitable for the employees so that the staff shall replicate the organizations efforts in terms of better productivity at reduced costs. The existing scenario which the businesses needs to switch over does not requisite billion dollar investments into acquiring new infrastructure or new facilities, rather small variations in the working conditions can make a big difference. Therefore this research paper does not embarks upon analyzing how to change the business processes rather it analyses what to change in the business processes.

2. Objectives of the research

The objectives of the research are:

- Identifying innovative work behavior practices that can optimize the productivity levels from cost – benefit perspective.
- Evaluating a model conjoining several parameters based upon which the organizations can classify and select the appropriate innovative work practice that can suit their business model.

3. Literature review

There have been researches on the need of innovation in the working aspects of the organizations. The need of bringing innovation at workplace was first brought by Joseph Schumpeter (1934) providing that management and workspace innovation needs to be seen as a creation of a new domain within the entity. Van & Lepine (1998) further added that implementation of innovation process requisites a dipole process equipping prior thought processing and then executing. M.A. West & Bunce, D. (1995) have provided that individual psychology of upbringing new innovations by one self are determined by the individuals perceptions about the performance of the overall team and fellow colleagues. Axtell, C.M. (2000) has provided the need for innovation at the shop floor factory and industry level. Further steps and measures have also been discussed upon for bringing innovation at the shop floor level. Houghton & DiLiello (2006) provided that innovative processes can be critical for the rise of the organization. It is the impact made by every individual that cumulates to become an organizational success. Schneider & Macey (2008) researched that the organizations which include employee benefit concerns in the HR policies are in turn benefited with increased efforts from the motivated employees. Shi, K. et al (2010) made a study on how individual employees behavior is affected by the type of changes in the leadership processes.

4. Research methodology

Research methodology comprising applied research methodology coalesced with participatory observation has been deployed comprehensively. Empirical evidences have been utilized for analyzing the existing impact based studies in implementing innovating work practices at different kinds of workspaces. A self-prepared – self-directed survey approach was chosen to obtain data for the research. Companies operating on pan India basis were chosen and their employees were handed over the questionnaire through e-mail and physical hand over. We experienced a response rate of 81% as a total of 450 questionnaires were distributed and 365 were validly returned. Our survey composed of 28% employees who have been working with the present employer for less than 2 year, 41% employees who have been with the current employer for time period between 2 – 7 years and 31% having served more than 7 years. The age group served was between 21 years to 55 years. Thus our survey acted as a comprehensive docket researching on needs of multiple types of organizations. Further the methodology of AELS: Active – Emphatic Listening Scale was adopted to research about the psychological factors in more efficient manner.

5. Research analysis

Innovation has always been considered to be the undisclosed ingredient behind the unprecedented unanticipated business progression. Work place interests have started getting a place in the modern business management lexicon. Its origination can be traced back to incessantly increasing apprehension for the need of job and personal life equilibrium.

- **Evaluation of different kinds of innovations at the work space**

It is an established fact that innovative work management practices possess the potential to bring an entity at par with the international standards. Hundreds and thousands of innovative practices can be developed based upon the requirements of the organization. This research paper provides an illustrative list in this section providing an insight into how innovations can be worked upon:

Collaborative Work Stations

By 2019, the prices of real estate industry have already crossed the marks which were once thought to be the zenith points of prices in real estate. In this situation, where an organization is compelled to reduce the price of the output under the purview of intensely competitive market, has to bear incessantly increasing employee expenditure and is burdened with rising cost of input products, the MSME organizations are in no position to place big sized infrastructures in their balance sheets. Therefore collaborative working may be adopted wherein work stations may be shared amongst several employees. For instance, Wi-Fi facility may be provided for entire organization rather than using several Local Area Networks (LAN) for multiple teams.

Further team members of a single team may be arranged to sit together at the workspace. Supervision and direct guidance from the seniors can aid in maximizing the work exposure of the junior level employees. Small rooms may be dedicated for one to one conversations between the teams or colleagues. Separate “break out spaces” may be provided for quick refreshment for the employees. Collaborative working not only saves costs of the corporation but also reduces the quantum of environmental resource consumption.

Activity Based Working (ABW)

ABW encompasses establishment of different kinds of workspace settings for different kinds tasks. In a consultancy firm PQR providing multiple services like IT services, tax consultancy and call center outsourcing services, different kinds of work place may be created. Like the IT department workstations may be shared while the call center department may be provided separate work desks. The internal tech support IT staff may be placed near the IT department. The theory of ABW further suggests that the employees should be encouraged to form their own work collaborations. The grouping by HR department may not be in the choice of the staff or the new colleagues may not be familiar with each other. If the office employees are provided with only the output requirement and are provided the necessary autonomy they can provide better results in limited time period. ABW methodology provides setting up the office infrastructure in the way the employees prefer it to be. This inculcates the feeling of self-empowerment at each individual employee level that their choices and preferences are valued. This aspect of intrinsic motivation can result in huge enhancement in the productivity levels. MNC's like Hershey and Sodexo have installed the ABW policy at a massive level in their operational structure.

Free Address Workspace (FAW)

This methodology implies following the open desk policy meaning thereby the work stations are not assigned to any particular employee or a team. The work stations can be used by any team and multiple teams on different occasions. Such a methodology is optimum for corporations whose employees have to travel frequently. The major advantage that is offered by FAW is the optimal utilization of the real estate. Sapiient Company has been active in adopting the free address concept in its workspace design in its US offices.

Running Work Spaces

It has been researched that office staff spends 75% of the total working hours in the sitting posture. While human body has been designed with much flexibility and agility which is meant to be used for active movement, sitting for prolonged hours can result in chronic decline in human health along with the muscle skeleton being exposed towards carcinogenic threats. Any decline in the health of the employees results in huge decline in the overall productivity of the organization.

Therefore in addition to the standard work spaces, few innovative work stations may be installed. Such work stations shall be equipped with running facilities and standing facilities. If considered successful, such workstations can replace the entire traditional work spaces. It has been substantiated that healthy employees can contribute a whopping 12% enhancement in productivity than compared with sick and unhappy employees.

Office Home – Hybrid model of operation

Our survey has resulted that 90% of the employees prefer to opt for work from home alternative for at least 1 day in a week. While only 19% Indian corporates in our survey included the option of work from home policy in their HR policy. Work from home policy has to be seen as a must for envisaging better return on time being invested by the employees. It was further confirmed that in a tech coding firm, where the employee used to take 12 hours for testing a given code in the office premises, the employee took 3 hours less to do the same in the home environment. It was further seen that where the employee was provided with multiple work from home options continuously for a number of weeks, the employee took 5 hours more than what could be done in 12 hours.

Therefore the Indian corporates can adopt a balanced mix of working from office and work from home policy. Segmentation may also be made based upon the classification of the employee designation. For example, the manager segment may be given 2 days work from home alternative, while the assistant manager segment may be provided 1 day option. Such fragmentation can work wonders if implemented in a well-planned manner.

Agile Working

Agile working is the grant of absolute liberty to the employees in selecting the mode of operation. It is the most recently developed innovative work practice which crosses beyond any restriction that can be imposed by the management. This provides unconditional autonomy to the employees in selecting how they would work. It will be the choice of employees, whether they would prefer working on regular work stations or running work spaces. They would prefer 100% office working scenario or home working conditions or adoption of hybrid model framed as per their convenience. Under the agile working condition the methodology is to provide comprehensive flexibility to the employees in the max possible manner. It provides maximized sensation of self-empowerment and supreme job satisfaction level. However the deployment of required IT setup to manage entire employee framework is challenging for many enterprises. Agile working scenario may be best suited to the large cap corporations.

- **Identification of appropriate mode of innovative work model - TIMES Model**

An organization can apply several kinds of innovative work designs. However meticulous considerations must be given to every kind of innovative work practice to identify whether such work practice can be suited as per the business model. For instance, suppose a BPO consultancy cum call center outsourcing firm, ABC implements the policy of running work desks an innovative work behavior wherein the employees are provided with work stations equipped with tread mills or other running machines. This model is meant to fail since if the employees are running while speaking to the clients, they will not be able to provide their absolute attention to the client's concern and will not be able to even provide their full assistance to the client which can damage the entire business model of ABC firm. Thus the said firm needs

to apply some other innovative practice such as providing employees with natural infrastructure wherein they can stay afresh while communicating with the clients.

This process would therefore require paying attention to even the minutest details which does not seem plausible for all kinds of enterprises. Therefore TIMES model has been devised which links the fundamental attributes that are required to make an employee satisfied with the requirements of the business entity. TIMES Model aims at providing a platform for integrating individual employees aspirations and the organizations desires.

Figure 1: TIMES Model for identification, evaluation and selection of apposite innovative work practice

TIMES Model stands for Transcendence, Independence, Motivation, Empowerment, Size and Type of the Organization which are discussed herein below. Any innovation business practice that can be applied in an organization must satisfy every component of the TIMES model. If it matches the requirements of the model, the management can consider the adoption of the policy.

Transcendence

The dictionary meaning of the term transcendence provides the meaning of being supreme. Transcendence in the context of the corporate scenario implies the feeling of an employee being superior to the other colleagues. Transcendence component under the TIMES model requires imbuing the sensation of being valued and being given importance to an individual employee.

It has been observed that under the team initiatives, the recognition is often not percolated down to the root level. Persistent acknowledgment of the leadership without the individual appraisal leads the transformation of a satisfied employee to a disgruntled employee. Therefore the innovation practice that is being considered to be implemented must imbue the feeling of transcendence in the minds of each and every targeted personnel. The targeted group must be left with an intrinsic conscious that his presence holds importance in the organizational hierarchy and he must strive hard to make it better. For instance, a policy may be introduced wherein, after every successful assignment, an appreciative email shall be circulated by the top leadership throughout the organization mentioning the name of all the team members. This minuscule initiative can stir an employee emotions to work more hard to get more such recognition at the organization wide level.

Independence

Whether it is an organizational framework or a personal setting, independence and autonomy are imperative to make an individual contemplate that his opinions and suggestions matters. In the organizational context, absolute centralization cannot be performed in the long term scenario. A balanced mix of decentralization with overall supervision is required to bring the most out of the staff. Therefore any new business practice must not be limited to a particular level in the organization rather it should be effectively spread out across the entity. For instance, an organization working solely on the Top – down model is not perceived as an employee friendly and desirable association. Rather a comfortable mix of Top – down model with Bottom – up approach can work wonders.

Motivation

If the employees feels as if they are being pulled compulsarily at the work place daily then such employees shall not stay in the organization for a long term shooting up the attrition rate which is perceived highly negatively at the industry level. The continuous process of interviewing, recruiting, selecting employees involve humungus costs and substantial investment of time resource. By changing the way how business processes are carried out, it can be ensured that employees stay contended with their present positions and job profiles. This not only improves the organization's market standing but also provides long term committed work force providing good quality work in less time with less costs. For instance, an innovation practice involves conducting periodical motivational sessions of employees and conducting career consulting sessions. This shifts the onus on the employees that it is now their turn to do something for the organization which is taking much care for them.

Empowerment

This phase involves the development of emotional, mental and divine wellbeing of the human resources. The personnel working at a position must have the sensation of being someone not just in the organization but also at the societal level. The more is the feeling of being empowered the more is satisfaction level with the job. This involves application of multiple roles such as career advancement, job promotions. Self empowerment further encompasses the aspect of regular encouragement of the employees. Without regularly encouraging the employee, he may become a robot which may not be appropriate in the business interests. The enterprise has been spending much on learning and development of the employees to produce learned employees and not robots following the plain commands of the superiors. An all inclusive environment needs to be created where in the human resources are encouraged on making greater employee participation in the organizational processes. This attribute also acts as the residual characteristic in the TIMES Model which encompasses the components that have been left behind the other specific attributes.

Activity Based Working methodology is a classic illustration of innovative work space approach conjoining employee independence, self-empowerment and aspects of intrinsic enthusiasm.

Size & Type of the organization

The type of innovative business practice that a business intends to apply must be suitable to the size and type of organization. A particular innovative work practice may be suitable for a specific entity operating in a specific industry, that innovation may not practicable at all for any other type entity. Like the agile working condition may not be suited for small cap organization. Similar a front end hotel industry operating on guest satisfaction cannot apply agile working methodology irrespective of the size of its operations, while the agile working scenario may be adopted for back end support staff of the hotel like the IT department.

6. Conclusion

Satisfaction at the workplace can be construed as a comprehensive experience of contentment, positivity and the willingness of aligning oneself with the business objectives. It improves the employee's health, reduces stress, quality of life and overall organizational efficiency and effectiveness. This motivates the employees and rightly bridges up the space amongst individual aspirations and business entities requirements. Therefore the existing employees work with better dedication and commitment and thereby brings better output to the business eliminating the need for the management to adopt the hiring and firing model.

Every industry needs to reconsider how long their existing work place stratagem can sustain the growing requirements and expectations of their business. Today the Key to Productivity is the implementation of an effective and innovative work space strategy which encompasses efficient infrastructural space utilization targeting improvement in performance of physical assets by up to 45%, ensures greater office work to personal life balance, bringing much needed flexibility and mobility for the personnel and strikes on achieving collaborative working within the organization. Implementing innovative processes must be seen as a separate process and considerable amount of attention by the top management needs to be provided for bringing the most out of the innovative process.

7. References

- Axtell, C.M., Holman, D.J., Unsworth, K.L., Wall, T.D., P.E. Waterson & E. Harrington (2000). Shopfloor innovation: Facilitating the suggestion and implementation of ideas. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*. 73, 265-285.
- Belk, R. (2013). "Extended Self in a Digital World." *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 40, No. 3, 477-500, DOI: 10.1086/671052.
- Cowan-Sahadath, K. (2010). "Business transformation: Leadership, integration and innovation - A case study." *International Journal of Project Management*, 28 (2010) 395–404,
- Cross, J., Earl, M., & Sampler, J. (1997). Transformation of the IT Function at British Petroleum. *MIS Quarterly*, 21(4), 401-423. DOI: 10.2307/24972.
- Dannemiller, K.D., Jacobs, R.W. (1992). Changing the way organizations change: a revolution of common sense. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science* 28 (4), 480–498.
- Durante, Giacomo and Turvani, Margherita (2018). Coworking, the Sharing Economy, and the City: Which Role for the 'Coworking Entrepreneur'?, *MDPI, UrbanSci*. 2, 83.
- Housman, Michael, and Dylan Minor (2016). "Workplace Design: The Good, the Bad, and the Productive." *Harvard Business School Working Paper*, No. 16-147,
- M.A. West, Bunce, D. (1995), Personality and perceptions of group climate factors as predictors of individual innovation at work, *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 44, 199-215.
- M. D. Fottler, G. T. Savage, & J. D. Blair (Eds.), *Advances in health care management* (Vol. 2, pp. 315–340).
- Oswald, Andrew J., Proto, Eugenio and SgROI, Daniel. (2015) Happiness and productivity, *Journal of Labor Economics*, 33 (4). pp. 789-822.
- Philippa M. Dall, Cormac G. Ryan, Malcolm H. Granat & P. Margaret Grant (2011) Sitting patterns at work: objective measurement of adherence to current recommendations, *Ergonomics*, 54:6, 531-538, DOI: 10.1080/00140139.2011.570458.
- Shi, K., Liu, J. & Siu, O. L. (2010). Transformational leadership and employee well-being: The mediating roles of trust in leaders and self-efficacy. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 59(3), 454–479.
- Tynan, R. (2005). The effects of threat sensitivity and face giving on dyadic psychological safety and upward communication. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 35, 223–247.
- Van De Ven, A., Poole, M., 1995. Explaining development and change in organizations. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20(3), 510–540.
- Van Dyne L, LePine JA (1998). Predicting voice behavior in work groups. *J. Appl. Psychol.*, 83(6): 853-868.
- Wang, P., & Rode, J. C. (2010). Transformational leadership and follower creativity: The moderating effects of identification with leader and organizational climate. *Human Relations*, 63, 1105–1128.
- Wright, T. A., & Staw, B. M. (1999). Affect and favorable work outcomes two longitudinal tests of the happy-productive worker thesis. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 20(1), 1–23.